

From Data-Centred to Data-Driven: Gaia-X and the Architecture of Smart Public Administration

Position paper for the domains of geoinformation, the public sector, and smart cities and regions of Gaia-X Hub Portugal

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From Data-Centred to Data-Driven: Gaia-X and the Architecture of Smart Public Administration

About the Document

This position paper is the result of a collaboration within the Gaia-X Hub Portugal, specifically from the Technical Working Group on Smart Communities led by [Ubiwhere](#).

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARTE	Agência para a Reforma Tecnológica do Estado
CDS	Cross-sectoral Data Sharing
CIM	Comunidade Intermunicipal
CRISP-DM	Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary Application profile for data portals in Europe
DGAEP	Direção-Geral da Administração e do Emprego Público
DIKW	Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom
DL	Deep Learning
DPL	Data Protection Legislation
DQ	Data Quality
DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
DS	Data Science
DW	Data Warehouses
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GAI	Generative AI
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GXFS	Gaia-X Federation Services
GXDCH	Gaia-X Digital Clearing House
HVDs	Public Sector High Value Datasets
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDS-RAM	Reference Architecture Model

IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estatística
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information technology
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
KDD	Knowledge Discovery in Databases
ML	Machine Learning
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interface with Linked Data
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NUTS	Nomenclatura das Unidades Territoriais para Fins Estatísticos
OLAP	Online Analytical Processing
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SDG	Sustainability Development Goals
SEMMA	Sample, Explore, Modify, Model, Assess
SLA	Service-Level Agreement
SCWG	Smart Communities Working Group
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
TDSP	Team Data Science Process
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

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Informative Note

This document was produced by the members of the Technical Working Group on Smart Communities of the Portuguese Gaia-X Hub, following the work of the document produced in 2024 entitled 'Positioning for smart cities: Gaia-X and the future of data-centric public administration'.

Executive Summary

Public administrations are increasingly required to navigate complex streams of information and ensure efficient, transparent, and citizen-centred services. The transition from data-centred to data-driven governance represents a decisive step in this evolution, moving beyond the accumulation of data toward the active use of this data as a strategic asset for decision-making.

On one hand, data-driven systems extend and enhance the scope of public services and sovereign tasks. On the other hand, they introduce increasingly complex ecosystems of public and private stakeholders in digital value chains. This reality reinforces the urgency of adopting resilient and sustainable approaches to urban and regional governance, particularly as administrations face pressing transformations in energy, mobility, and infrastructure sectors.

The purpose of this paper is to explain and describe the principles of data-driven public administration and organisational and technical requirements to achieve it. Section 1 introduces the general context of the transition towards data-driven governance and highlights legal and administrative challenges. Section 2 analyses how data is organised, shared, and federated across different administrative levels, addressing semantic alignment, spatial coherence, and trust mechanisms essential for data governance. Section 3 examines the critical security and privacy challenges inherent to smart city data. Section 4 highlights the growing interconnection between data management and Artificial Intelligence, transforming data into actionable knowledge.

The paper also examines, in section 6, some real-world use cases that demonstrate the practical implementation of data-driven principles in public administration, illustrating how federated data spaces and interoperability standards can be applied to improve governance, optimise resource management, and foster innovation.

1. Introduction

The digital transformation of public administration represents a fundamental shift from a traditional siloed approach to governance towards a more integrated, intelligent and citizen-centred decision making. As governments worldwide embrace digital technologies, the paradigm is evolving from digitising existing processes to fundamentally questioning their relevance and necessity. This transformation offers an opportunity to reimagine how public services are conceived, delivered and optimised through data intelligence, offering new approaches that better serve citizens' lives and leverage the full potential of digital capabilities.

The shift to data-driven governance implies the creation of a unified state digital ecosystem with data and algorithms at the centre, building real-time data exchange networks to deliver improved public services. Such paradigm calls for rethinking of public administration principles ensuring the transition from an electronic state to a digital one¹.

This transformation is particularly relevant in the European context, where Gaia-X² empowers businesses, individuals and governments with secure, transparent, and sovereign control over data through a decentralised cloud infrastructure, establishing a federated secure data platform for Europe, whereby data is shared, with users retaining control over their data access and usage.

Public administration across Portugal faces significant challenges related to data fragmentation, interoperability gaps, and the absence of coherent information topologies that cross administrative and territorial boundaries. As public services become increasingly data-driven, big data technologies and software products are turning into key tools for managing technological processes in real time, enabling more efficient delivery of public services to citizens¹.

Gaia-X infrastructure and ecosystem is built upon European principles such as freedom, equality, and fundamental citizen rights. These values are safeguarded through mechanisms including data security, GDPR compliance, transparency and interoperability³. This positions

¹ Yuhno, A. (2022). Digital Transformation: Exploring big data Governance in Public Administration. *Public Organization Review*, vol. 24, pp. 335-349. DOI: 10.1007/s11115-022-00694-x. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11115-022-00694-x>

² Gaia-X. (n.d.). *Gaia-X*. <https://gaia-x.eu/>

³ Gaia-X Hub Germany. (n.d.). *Gaia-X explained*. <https://gaia-x-hub.de/en/gaia-x-explained/>

Gaia-X as a critical enabler for the development of smart communities and data-driven public administration that respects European values of digital sovereignty and citizen privacy.

Central to Gaia-X's vision is the concept of Local Data Spaces, with Data Spaces being defined as an 'interoperable framework, based on common governance principles, standards, practices and enabling services, that enables trusted data transactions between participants'⁴. The objective of Gaia-X is to advance and strengthen the European data economy through a type of ownership that is distributed over many actors - yet is not state-owned - building on top of Data Spaces with a decentralised/federated ecosystem⁵ built on trust, enabling more stakeholders to join and collaborate confidently.

This position paper aims to establish a comprehensive framework for implementing data-driven public administration within the Gaia-X ecosystem, specifically addressing the challenges and opportunities for Portuguese public administration in transitioning from data-centred to data-driven governance models. By leveraging the federated data infrastructure capabilities of Gaia-X, Portuguese public administration can serve as a model for other European jurisdictions seeking to implement smart, responsive, and privacy-preserving government services.

⁴ DSSC. (n.d.). *Introduction - Key Concepts of Data Spaces*.
<https://dssc.eu/space/bv15e/766061351/Introduction+-+Key+Concepts+of+Data+Spaces>

⁵ Gaia-X. (2021). *Gaia-X and European Smart Cities and Communities white paper*.
<https://gaia-x.eu/wp-content/uploads/files/2021-10/Gaia-X%20SCC%20white%20paper.pdf>

2. Information Topology

Common European Data Spaces⁶ are an initiative that aims to build a trustworthy and secure environment for data sharing among European companies, organisations and citizens. The coordination of multiple heterogeneous European entities that generate, collect and/or store data across many different fields (health, social, business, among others) call for the definition of a Digital Governance Plan that preserves a structured and distributed access to these Data Spaces, across multiple organisational, territorial and infrastructural layers.

This Digital Governance Plan focuses on safeguarding the unique contribution of these many different stakeholders across these Common European Data Spaces. Firstly, by preserving data sovereignty, through laws and regulations of the country or jurisdiction where data is generated, collected, or stored; this means that different stakeholders are imbued with the legal authority to govern how their data is accessed, used, and protected. Secondly, by creating a federated data infrastructure, that allows the access and analysis of data from multiple, distributed entities, without physically moving or copying the data, in order to preserve both the privacy and ownership of the data. And thirdly, designing a semantic interoperability system, that allows for different systems to exchange data and have that data be understood with the same meaning by all stakeholders involved; going beyond simply generating, collecting and storing data, it ensures that the context and meaning of the information is also shared and correctly interpreted across Data Spaces.

Within the Gaia-X initiative, Information Topology is a foundational concept: it refers to the architectural mechanisms that handle the generation, collection and storage of data across this multi-stakeholder environment. Contributing to Common European Data Spaces initiative, this Gaia-X architectural framework defines a sovereign digital ecosystem supporting a clearly delineated topology of data ownership, access rights, provenance, and processing governance. This Gaia-X ecosystem is federated by design, allowing for public sector entities to act simultaneously as data providers, consumers, brokers, depending on the context and administrative level. Figure 1 illustrates the federated design of the Gaia-X framework, based on the work done by the National Institute of Standards and Technology

⁶ European Commission. (2025). *Common European data spaces*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

(NIST) on Cloud Federations⁷; it shows the Gaia-X Trust Framework three plane structure for data spaces, centered around a Trust plane that extends across all managed ecosystems for interoperable, trusted relationships⁸.

Gaia-X Technical Compatibility as the basis for ecosystem interoperability

Figure 1 - Gaia-X Ecosystem interoperability based on NISTs Cloud Federation Reference Architecture⁸

This model is reinforced by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), another organisation focused on establishing and promoting standards for Data Spaces, aiming to create a global standard for International Data Spaces (IDS) and related technologies; its Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM)⁹, is a layered architecture that reflects the separation of concerns between business, functional, information, system, and process responsibilities, reinforcing important paradigms of data sovereignty, interoperability, and trusted ecosystems as foundational principles for data space architectures as federated digital infrastructures.

Information topology is not agnostic to the spatial and administrative structures of a country. In fact, the effectiveness of smart governance is deeply influenced by how well the

⁷ National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). (2020). *The NIST Cloud Federation Reference Architecture*. <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.500-332.pdf>

⁸ Gaia-X. (2025). *Gaia-X Context (Architecture Document)*. https://docs.gaia-x.eu/technical-committee/architecture-document/25.05/gaia-x_context/

⁹ International Data Spaces Association. (2023). *IDS-RAM-4*. <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/ids-ram-4>

information topology aligns with a nation's territorial and institutional geometry. In Portugal, the design of information topology must accommodate the decentralised, yet interdependent nature of public services, with a strong municipal tradition and intermunicipal coordination backbone.

Work started in developing these legal and regulatory frameworks: from the side of the European Union, with the Data Act¹⁰ and the Data Governance Act¹¹, addressing the challenges of the Information Topology concept while ensuring fair access, user rights and protection of personal data. On the national level, as is the case of Portugal, both the 'Regulamento Geral de Proteção de Dados' (RGPD), the Portuguese enforcement of the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹², as well as the 'Plano de Ação para a Transição Digital'¹³ (Action Plan for Digital Transition), a strategic agenda developed by the Portuguese government to accelerate the digitisation of the country's infrastructure, offer a distinctive laboratory for deploying such architectures in a territorially sensitive manner.

2.1 Spatial and Administrative Divisions of Data

The articulation of this information topology in public administrations requires anchoring data structures to formal administrative boundaries and spatial relationships. This approach enables jurisdictional clarity, and coordinated governance across all levels of the public sector, as well as simplifying semantic consistency across heterogeneous domains. Smart data administrations emerge from governments' necessity to effectively manage and use data in order to enhance decision-making and drive innovation; leveraging data-driven insights, governments can optimise operations, personalise services, and manage risks across their local ecosystem, ultimately improving citizens' everyday life.

The governance and organisation of public sector data in these smart public administrations must reflect the territorial architectures in which governments operate. Whether in unitary states, federal systems, or multi-level governance frameworks such as the European Union, the territorial expansion of data introduces persistent challenges and structuring needs.

¹⁰ European Union. (2023). Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32023R2854>

¹¹ European Union. (2022). Regulation (EU) 2022/868 on European data governance. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R0868>

¹² European Union. (n.d.). General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

¹³ Portugal Digital. (2020). *Plano de Ação para a Transição Digital de Portugal*. <https://www.portugal.gov.pt/gc22/portugal-digital/plano-de-acao-para-a-transicao-digital-pdf.aspx>

Within a Gaia-X-aligned data infrastructure, these spatial-administrative divisions constitute not just governance constraints but functional data boundaries, each with specific implications for interoperability, sovereignty, and usage rights.

Across various territorial domains—supranational, national, regional, intermunicipal, municipal, and sub-municipal—several shared considerations emerge. These common factors must be systematically embedded into the information topology of smart public sector data architectures.

2.1.1 Common Considerations across Territorial Domains

At every territorial level, legal competence defines the scope of services, rights, and obligations. This legal framework determines who produces the data, who owns or governs the data and who may access, aggregate, or federate the data. As such, data stewardship roles must be territorially contextualised. Gaia-X introduces roles like data provider, consumer, intermediary and federator (identity provider), which can and often should correspond to the specific territorial authority responsible for the service domain in question.

The effectiveness of data reuse in public administration depends on the vertical interoperability across different levels of territorial governance, ensuring the seamless exchange and interpretation of data. In the European domain, important statistical indicators can be defined at multiple levels (municipal, regional, national) and must be interoperable with relevant European metrics such as those defined by organisations as the Eurostat, or by important surveys and reports produced by international organisations, such as the Urban Audit¹⁴ and relevant ISO standards¹⁵.

In achieving semantic consistency across territorial domains, the shared challenge of harmonising indicators, by having a shared structure that deals with different units of measurement, frequencies, and metadata schemas is addressed; this is where Gaia-X's

¹⁴ European Commission. (n.d.). *Urban Audit*.

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/themes/urban-development/audit_en

¹⁵ International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (n.d.). *Standards*.

<https://www.iso.org/standards.html>

compliance/trust framework^{16 17} or the IDSA's vocabulary alignment mechanisms¹⁸ become operationally critical.

Territorial domains are also rarely neatly nested. Instead, public service delivery often involves overlapping jurisdictions, which creates the need for multi-territorial anchoring of datasets. A single data product (e.g., pollution readings, traffic congestion, social service usage) may be relevant to more than one administrative domain. Therefore, information topology must accommodate multi-scalar referential tagging, making it clear which territorial authorities are entitled to access, interpret, and act upon the data; territorially scoped policies must also be technically expressible and automatically enforceable within the Gaia-X federation. To curb the differences across territorial data domains, Gaia-X framework proposes:

- clear governance rules for data lifecycle management;
- transparency and traceability of data transformations;
- federated trust frameworks, where each domain governs its Data Space autonomously but within a shared interoperability and policy compliance structure;
- a common spatial ontology and referencing model, that enables data exchange, aggregation and policy monitoring across domains.

All of this is grounded in two complementary elements namely the Specification of Gaia-X Technical and the Specification of Gaia-X Compliance, that comprise the Gaia-X Trust Framework.

2.1.2 Administrative Divisions in the Portuguese domain

In the Portuguese context, the interplay between municipal, intermunicipal, regional and national levels is especially salient when embedding Data Spaces into public administration. Portugal is administratively divided into 308 *municípios* (municipalities), grouped into 21 intermunicipal communities (*Comunidades Intermunicipais*, CIM), which in turn nest within the 7 NUTS II (Nomenclatura das Unidades Territoriais para fins estatísticos) statistical

¹⁶ Gaia-X. (2024). *Gaia-X Compliance Criteria for Cloud Services (Compliance Document)*. <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/policy-rules-committee/compliance-document/24.06/criteria/>

¹⁷ Gaia-X. (n.d.). *Gaia-X Trust Framework*. <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/policy-rules-committee/trust-framework/22.10/>

¹⁸ International Data Spaces Association. (2023). *Interoperability Framework in Energy Data Spaces*. https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Position-paper-Energy-in-teroperability-framework-v0.9-1.pdf

regions. National-level governance remains vertically integrated via ministries and central agencies (e.g., INE, DGAEP, ARTE), which serve as aggregators, regulators, and custodians of macro-level datasets, ensuring compliance with European and international standards.

The spatial structuring of data assets, from the municipal to the national scale, forms the backbone of a robust public sector Data Space architecture. For instance, ISO 37120¹⁹ defines a globally recognised structure for collecting and reporting data across key service areas (governance, health, energy, environment, mobility) through a set of indicators that measure the performance of city services and quality of life, based on the UN's Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs)²⁰. This standard serves not only as a performance benchmarking tool but also as a guide for spatial data governance. This spatial alignment is crucial for developing federated data spaces that are both locally responsive and globally interoperable, in keeping with the Gaia-X principle of data sovereignty with federation.

For instance, in the case of the Portuguese ecosystem, the energy consumption data gathered according to this standard must also be tagged with municipality codes (*Código INE*) to enable granular analysis and policy responses tailored to local conditions, while also allowing regional and national integration for benchmarking and planning. Standardised metrics must be aligned with the geographical specificity of different territories in order to allow for data aggregation and usage, providing metadata integrity and measurement coherence are maintained.

A complementary reference model for federated Data Spaces is the previously mentioned IDS-RAM²¹. The Data Space is structured in five layers: business, functional, information, system, and process. Spatial tagging becomes part of the Information Layer, where each 'data asset' (e.g. mobility flows, public service metrics, geospatial datasets) must carry ontology fields indicating the municipality's ID, CIM, and NUTS II region, in the case of the Portuguese domain. This allows semantically aware queries and interoperable datasets across administrative levels. Moreover, contract negotiation and usage control in the Functional Layer should embed jurisdictional scope—e.g. access rights for a CIM aggregator vs. single municipality.

¹⁹ International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2018). ISO 37120:2018: Sustainable cities and communities – Indicators for city services and quality of life.

<https://www.iso.org/standard/68498.html>

²⁰ United Nations. (n.d.). *THE 17 GOALS*. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

²¹ International Data Spaces Association. (2023). *IDS-RAM-4*.

<https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/ids-ram-4>

In public administration, roles such as data provider and data consumer may map neatly onto levels of governance: a municipal authority as data provider, an intermunicipal health agency as consumer, and a federated national statistical service as aggregator/intermediary. Under IDS-RAM's Business Layer, these roles should be clearly modelled and assigned with usage policies coordinated via Rulebook provisions.

2.2 Data Quality

When we talk about the future of smart cities and data-driven public services, one important thing must come first: data quality (DQ). Without good DQ, even the best systems or advanced technologies cannot work properly. Poor data leads to wrong decisions, mistrust from citizens, and inefficiencies that affect services and policies and citizens trust.

DQ is not only about having data. It's about having useful data. This means data must be correct (accuracy), complete (no missing parts), consistent (same format and logic everywhere), timely (updated when needed), accessible (easy to reach), and unique (not duplicated). These six dimensions are the base for understanding what 'good data' means.

In smart cities, many data sources are used at the same time—like traffic sensors, environmental monitors, or public transport systems. These real-time data streams are fast, change often, and sometimes have missing parts or signal loss. This makes it difficult to check if the data is complete and updated in time²².

Before Gaia-X, several studies already showed the importance of DQ in the context of smart cities. For example, McArdle and Kitchin²² pointed out problems with the truthfulness of data in Dublin's open and real-time data platforms. In another work, Cuno et al.²³ introduced the idea of an Urban Data Space, where city data is organised and connected to legal responsibilities. Choenni et al.²⁴ focused on how to manage city data, highlighting the need

²² G. McArdle & R. Kitchin. (2016). Improving the Veracity of Open and Real-Time Urban Data. *Built Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.2148/benv.42.3.457>

²³ Cuno, S., Bruns, L., Tcholtchev, N., Lämmel, P., & Schieferdecker, I. (2019). Data governance and sovereignty in urban data spaces based on standardized ICT reference architectures. *Data*, 4(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/data4010016>

²⁴ Choenni, S., Bargh, M. S., Busker, T., & Netten, N. (2022). Data governance in smart cities: Challenges and solution directions. *Journal of Smart Cities and Society*, 1(1), 31–51. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SCS-210119>

for quality control and building trust between actors in the system. Finally, Okafor et al.²⁵ showed that there are often misunderstandings between stakeholders when talking about DQ.

Gaia-X promises federated data spaces that embed data sovereignty and interoperability by design, yet the explicit management of DQ remains insufficiently integrated. Gaia-X promotes the use of self-descriptions, which let organisations define their data and services. However, right now there is no common agreement on which data quality dimensions (such as accuracy or completeness) should be included, or how to describe them in a standard way (like using DCAT-AP or DQV)^{26 27}.

Today, public administrations face many challenges with data quality. Often, data comes from different sources, with different formats, and is not regularly updated. Also, legacy systems make it hard to integrate and clean the data. Public administration usually lacks tools and resources to evaluate data quality in a structured way. This can result in duplicated records, wrong values, or even data that cannot be used at all.

Different people involved in city data ecosystems understand ‘data quality’ in different ways. For example, municipal managers, technology providers, and data analysts often have their own definitions and priorities. This creates confusion and disagreements when trying to work together²⁵.

At the same time, many public administrations still work with older datasets that were not designed to be shared or integrated. These legacy datasets often do not include basic information about where the data came from or how it was collected. Without this provenance metadata, it becomes hard to verify the full history of the data when it is exposed to others through IDS Connectors²⁸.

²⁵ Okafor, C. C., Ferrer-Conill, R., & Helle, S. (2023). Dimensions of Data Quality for Values in Smart Cities Datafication Practices. *AoIR Selected Papers of Internet Research*.

<https://doi.org/10.5210/spir.v2023i0.13475>

²⁶ Otto, B. (2022). A federated infrastructure for European data spaces. *Communications of the ACM*, 65(4), 44–45. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3512341>

²⁷ Martella, C., Martella, A., & Longo, A. (2024). European data spaces for urban digital twins: User- and implementation-driven recommendations. In *2024 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData)*, 5496–5505. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData62323.2024.10826100>

²⁸ Cuno, S., Bruns, L., Tcholtchev, N., Lämmel, P., & Schieferdecker, I. (2019). Data Governance and Sovereignty in Urban Data Spaces Based on Standardized ICT Reference Architectures. *Data*, 4(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/data4010016>

In practice, current pilots mostly describe how data can be accessed and used, not how good or reliable data actually is. As a result, data users cannot compare datasets based on measurable data quality scores, and automated service-level agreement (SLA) negotiation becomes impossible.

Also, in federated Data Spaces, there are many roles—such as provider, consumer, operator, and federator. This makes it unclear who is responsible for checking and maintaining the data quality over time²⁹.

The AI Act makes things even more strict for smart city systems that are considered to be of 'high-risk.' These systems will need stronger evidence of data quality, but right now, the tools to do this are not fully ready or mature³⁰.

As Gaia-X continues to evolve, several important questions remain open regarding how DQ should be implemented and managed in smart city contexts. One key challenge is defining a standard set of DQ dimensions for self-descriptions. While ISO 25012 and ISO 8000 provide a broad range of quality characteristics, it is still unclear which of these should be considered essential for smart-city assets in Gaia-X. Should accuracy and completeness be mandatory? Or should the minimum requirements change depending on the domain? Moreover, any standard would also need a trusted method of certification to ensure it can be applied consistently across federated data spaces.

Beyond conventional data quality frameworks, the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability), offer a compelling lens through which to evaluate smart-city data. These principles naturally reinforce key DQ dimensions³¹: findable and accessible data strengthens completeness and consistency, while interoperable and reusable data promotes accuracy and reliability across systems. Yet, a critical question arises: does Gaia-X actively consider the alignment of its components with FAIR principles, or is this synergy still an overlooked opportunity? Could a deliberate integration of FAIR

²⁹ Heinbach, C., Gessler, J., Rychlik, H., Stecenko, C., Wieker, H., & Schulz, W. H. (2024). Sharing Business Data Securely. *Journal of Telecommunications and the Digital Economy*, 12(4), 66-84. <https://doi.org/10.18080/jtde.v12n4.1037>

³⁰ Choenni, S., Bargh, M. S., Busker, T., & Netten, N. (2022). Data governance in smart cities: Challenges and solution directions. *Journal of Smart Cities and Society*, 1(1), 31–51. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SCS-210119>

³¹ OpenAIRE. (n.d.). *How to make your data FAIR*. <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>

practices serve as a missing link to achieving truly trustworthy and high-quality³² data in federated smart-city environments, or will this remain an open challenge for practitioners and policymakers alike?

Another open direction involves handling DQ as close as possible to the source of data. With the growth of edge computing, it is now technically possible to apply basic quality checks - such as detecting abnormal sensor values or signal drift using methods like Kalman filters - before the data is sent to the cloud or to IDS Connectors. But doing this without adding too much latency remains a technical problem that still needs research.

Human involvement remains important too. While many DQ tools now provide automated scoring, there are often situations where the system's evaluation doesn't match the expectations or knowledge of domain experts. Municipal data stewards must be able to understand these scores, question them when needed, and make corrections. But designing user interfaces that support this type of 'human-in-the-loop' stewardship—without adding too much complexity—is still a design challenge.

Many Gaia-X pilot projects today are focused on mobility data^{33 34}. However, each domain - whether it's energy, environment, or digital government - has different data patterns and quality needs. For example, energy data may be high-frequency but very structured, while environmental data may come from many heterogeneous sources. So an important research question is whether the DQ methods developed in one domain can really be reused in others.

Finally, we must consider the cost. Continuous data quality monitoring requires resources, tools, and sometimes new roles. For public administrations already under financial pressure, this is not easy. Future work should explore economic models that explain the return on

³² Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., et al. (2016). The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³³ Otto, B. (2022). A federated infrastructure for European data spaces. *Communications of the ACM*, 65(4), 44–45. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3512341>

³⁴ Kremer, M., Pohling, L., Gössling, G., Heinbach, C., & Sachweh, T., et al. (2023). An intelligent arrival time prediction service in a federated data ecosystem: The minimum viable demonstrator of the GAIA-X 4 ROMS research project. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, Paper 4331859. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4331859>

investment in DQ, and how these costs might be shared across multiple actors in a Data Space - such as data providers, consumers, and federators³⁵.

2.3 Data Federation

The future of public administration does not lie in centralising data, but in enabling its secure, governed, and impactful exchange across institutional and territorial boundaries. Data federation offers a decentralised model for managing and sharing data, allowing public entities to retain full control over their datasets while contributing to a broader, interconnected data ecosystem.

Data Federation enables information from multiple, distributed sources to be accessed and combined through a common technical and governance framework, without physically moving or duplicating the data. A core capability of federated systems is federated query answering, which provides users with a unified interface to access data from different sources³⁶, while ensuring that data policies and access controls are respected.

This architectural model is foundational to the development of Common European Data Spaces³⁷, sector-specific frameworks promoted by the European Commission to enable trusted, sovereign, and secure data sharing across organisations and borders in the EU. These Data Spaces are currently being developed across key domains such as health, energy, agriculture, and mobility, and are designed to facilitate collaboration between public and private actors through shared standards and governance rules.

To implement the European Strategy for Data and realise the full potential of these Data Spaces, interoperability and collaboration is essential. Gaia-X addresses this challenge by providing federation services that function both within and across Data Spaces³⁸, and a common compliance framework to deal with interoperability trust issues.

³⁵ Heinbach, C., Gessler, J., Rychlik, H., Stecenko, C., Wieker, H., & Schulz, W. H. (2024). Sharing Business Data Securely. *Journal of Telecommunications and the Digital Economy*, 12(4), 66-84. <https://doi.org/10.18080/jtde.v12n4.1037>

³⁶ Gu, Z., Corcoglioniti, F., Lanti, D., et al. (2022). A systematic overview of data federation systems. *Semantic Web*, 15(1), 107–165. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-223201>

³⁷ European Commission. (2025). *Common European data spaces*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

³⁸ Otto, B. (2022). A federated infrastructure for European data spaces. *Communications of the ACM*, 65(4), 44–45. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3512341>

This approach is especially relevant in the context of Portuguese public administration, as it is fragmented across departments and levels of government (local, regional, and national). Attempting to centralise all relevant data in a single repository would be not only technically complex but also legally sensitive. Federation offers a more feasible solution, preserving data sovereignty, respecting legal obligations, and supporting interoperability at both national and European levels.

To enable effective data federation, several core components must be in place. Gaia-X provides a reference framework through its Federation Services (GXFS), which includes: identity and trust management, federated service catalogue, data sovereignty - ensuring transparency and control of data usage -, and compliance mechanisms³⁹. These services ensure that data access is authenticated, authorised, and traceable, while data usage policies can specify conditions such as consent, geographical processing limits, or retention periods. In addition to the GXFS, the Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH)⁴⁰ plays a key role in validating and monitoring compliance across participants of this federated ecosystem, making sure they are up to the Gaia-X standards and ensuring that data exchanges occur within a secure and interoperable ecosystem.

Beyond technical infrastructure, federation also relies on common data standards (including semantic models, APIs, and metadata schemas) to ensure data can be interpreted and processed across systems. In the public sector, adopting standards such as DCAT-AP, NGS-LD, and shared ontologies is critical to enabling reuse and interoperability.

By adopting a federated model, the Public Sector can achieve several key benefits:

- Each entity retains control and ownership of its data;
- New entities can join without disrupting existing systems;
- Data access is controlled, traceable, and policy-driven, without requiring physical data movement;

³⁹ Gaia-X. (2021). *Gaia-X Federation Services (GXFS)*.
https://gaia-x.eu/wp-content/uploads/files/2022-01/Gaia-X_Federation_Services_White_Paper_1_December_2021.pdf

⁴⁰ Gaia-X. (n.d.). *Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH)*.
<https://gaia-x.eu/services-deliverables/digital-clearing-house/>

- Enables cross-sector innovation and collaboration, driving the development of new data-driven services and applications⁴¹;
- Seamless integration with European Data Spaces through shared frameworks and standards.

Gaia-X Architecture has a decentralised and federated design, allowing independent entities to work together while still having ownership over their data. This promotes data sovereignty and ensures trust among participants⁴¹. As Portugal builds its national vision for data-centred public administration, embracing the Gaia-X federation model can ensure alignment with European efforts while fostering secure, scalable, and citizen-centric public services.

2.4 Means of Integration

The integration of public sector data across multiple heterogeneous governing domains is one of the biggest challenges in realising Gaia-X vision for smart public administrations. Through data federation, Gaia-X seeks to decentralise the whole information/data topology structure in order to ensure that quality and trust are built in from collection to storage. Following this federated model approach, it preserves the capacity of this framework to connect diverse sources of data under a collection of shared principles, interoperable standards, and verifiable trust, that connect different data sources while allowing them to retain sovereignty over their own data.

The means of integration, in this context, should be understood as a layered and normative architecture, spanning across this Information Topology, and enabling autonomous actors/governments to interconnect their datasets while respecting spatial division and data quality requirements.

From prior analysis featured in this section, integration in a Gaia-X-compliant public administration framework can be summarised in four topics:

- Semantic and Ontological alignment;
- Territorial and Spatial Coherence;

⁴¹ Gaia-X. (2024). *Gaia-X Architecture: Building the Backbone of Trusted Digital Ecosystems*. https://gaia-x.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Architecture-Document_Marketing-Summary_2024-1.pdf

- Trust, Governance and Usage control;
- Data Quality as an Integrative and Interoperable Constraint.

2.4.1 Semantic and Ontological alignment

The first requirement for this framework is a Common Semantic Layer that ensures different systems, organisations and sectors can understand and exchange data beyond technical interoperability. Since different entities produce and consume heterogeneous data within the Gaia-X ecosystem, this common semantic layer establishes uniform vocabularies and ontologies, allowing for a more structured representation of this data and enabling the discovery, interpretation and relationship between different Data Providers and Data Consumers.

Data must carry metadata that reflects its technical properties (format, schema) but also administrative origin, jurisdictional validity and permissible uses. It should also be aligned with global standards for data indicators, such as the ones from the previously mentioned ISO 37120 related with city service indicators, but also ISO 19115/INSPIRE⁴² and other EU Core Vocabularies (location, person, organisation, service), as a technical guideline and shared ontology for information metadata, enhancing cross-border interoperability.

IDSA, with their IDS-RAM⁴³, stresses that integration between data assets should be achieved through a common semantic layer. For this, multiple intermediary elements participate in the exchange of data between Data Owners, Data Providers and Data Consumers. For the common semantic framework, two elements are particularly important: the IDS Broker, providing a service for data source registration, publication, maintenance and query through the Broker Service Provider; and the IDS Vocabulary, providing unambiguous identifiers through a formalised ontology of concepts and relationships, in a fundamental core vocabulary, through the Vocabulary Provider.

⁴² European Commission. (2013, October 29). *INSPIRE metadata implementing rules: Technical guidelines based on EN ISO 19115 and EN ISO 19119*.
https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/publications/inspire-metadata-implementing-rules-technical-guidelines-based-en-iso-19115-and-en-iso-19119_en

⁴³ International Data Spaces Association. (2023). *IDS-RAM-4*.
<https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/ids-ram-4>

Figure 2 - IDS Roles and Interactions⁴⁴

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) is an international consortium that develops web standards and guidelines for the growth, sustainability and accessibility of the world wide web, connecting information across the internet. In order to enable the representation and relationships between different groups of rich and complex data, W3C has its own Semantic Web stack, supported by technologies such as Resource Description Framework (RDF), SPARQL Query Language for RDF (SPARQL), JSON for Linked Data (JSON-LD), and Web Ontology Language (OWL), among others⁴⁵.

2.4.2 Territorial and Spatial Coherence

In the previous section on Spatial and Administrative Divisions of Data, a key step to guarantee the interoperability of data and emphasise data sovereignty, was the exploitation of Territorial Geometry for the governance of data. A territorial geometry ensures that legal, regulatory and policy frameworks are tied to the geography; this means that, be it at the local, national or EU level, regulations are respected. This is enabled by spatially anchoring datasets with the agreed upon identifiers and tying datasets and services to federation jurisdictions, while retaining interoperability; for instance, in the Portuguese context, it would require some combination of municipal codes and NUTS region codes, as well as INSPIRE geocodes.

⁴⁴ International Data Spaces Association. (2023). *Interaction of roles (Section 3.1.2, IDS-RAM 4)*. https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/ids-ram-4/layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3-layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3-1-business-layer/3_1_2_interaction_of_roles

⁴⁵ W3C. (2025). *Semantic Web Standards Wiki*. https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/wiki/Main_Page

A territorial geometry provides a structured way to distribute governance responsibilities across multiple levels. In this way, it is possible to preserve the nested and overlapping structure of governance, while avoiding fragmentation of jurisdiction by ensuring governance rules are coherent across the federation. This spatial coherence allows for federated analytics, through queries and benchmarks that can be executed across different domains without erasing their local specificity.

2.4.3 Trust, Governance and Usage control

Dataset integration across domains in Gaia-X framework must be achieved through trust rules, rather than specific pipelines. Through this Trust Framework, a set of rules serves as the minimum baseline to be part of the Gaia-X federation, providing a common trust and governance policy, as well as a basic interoperability level across individual ecosystems. Self-Descriptions are the trust framework key components expressing the information topology between datasets and services across domains: these descriptions are standardised, authentic (through cryptographical signatures) and evaluated automatically (compliance check via Digital Clearing Houses, tracking the usage of data).

For this purpose of Data Integration and Interoperability, Gaia-X Trust Framework outlines: clear role definitions (provider, consumer, intermediary, federator) at each territorial level; verifiable compliance at each data node, through the aforementioned self-descriptions for all participating Gaia-X entities, as well as specific certifications/credentials, in accordance with reputable standards (like W3C Verifiable Credentials Data Model)⁴⁶; and finally, specific usage policies are embedded with metadata to define access, retention or redistribution roles for controlled interoperability. This ensures that data sovereignty is preserved, and every actor participates in the federation on their own terms, through contractual guarantees that are enforceable and machine-interpretable.

Gaia-X Digital Clearing Houses (GXDCH)⁴⁷ are a network of verification nodes of the Gaia-X ecosystem, providing an automated and decentralised certification of data services and participants, in accordance with the Gaia-X Framework. While detached from the Gaia-X Association, the GXDCH is an operationalisation of the Gaia-X rules and recommendations,

⁴⁶ W3C. (2025, May 15). *Verifiable Credentials Data Model v2.0*.
<https://www.w3.org/TR/vc-data-model-2.0/>

⁴⁷ Gaia-X. (n.d.). *Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH)*.
<https://gaia-x.eu/services-deliverables/digital-clearing-house/>

enabling all participating parties to connect and exchange data, in a secure and federated manner, ensuring data sovereignty is never compromised.

2.4.4 Data Quality as an Integrative and Interoperable Constraint

For data to be usable across organisations and domains, consumers must trust the datasets they are requesting. Integration without Quality Assurance is meaningless, and interoperability between datasets and services depends on the consistency, completeness and reliability of data; quality assurance mechanisms are necessary to provide confidence in Data Space information topology. ISO 8000⁴⁸ is one of the latest standardisation efforts in describing the principles that help build the pathway for information and data quality.

For Gaia-X, integration means that Data Quality requirements must travel with the data, ensuring that when data flows across domains, it can be interpreted and integrated without any errors, allowing for integration without re-evaluation. For this, a quality level of the dataset (through metrics like accuracy, timeliness, representativeness) is recorded in metadata, and federation nodes enforce minimum quality thresholds for participation, ensuring that aggregated indicators are trustworthy. If quality requirements are met (metadata completeness, validated values, standardised units), the system framework can automate requests to process, match and combine datasets, removing the need for human intervention.

Portuguese initiatives are centered around the Gaia-X Hub Portugal⁴⁹ (led by [TICE.PT](https://tice.pt)) aligning Data Spaces in different sectors (health, mobility, energy, industry 4.0) with Gaia-X data quality requirements and quality constraints, making sure Portuguese laws and European norms are preserved for the digital administration of open data platforms. While not yet formally implemented, many commercial GXDCH providers already operate in Portugal, with the current roadmap for 2025 vouching for the pursuit of a pathway to establish an official GXDCH in Portugal⁵⁰.

For Gaia-X, integrating data within the information topology means ensuring all connected data assets are semantically aligned, territorial anchored, trust-compliant, quality-assured,

⁴⁸ International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2022). ISO 8000-1:2022: Data quality - Part 1: Overview. <https://www.iso.org/standard/81745.html>

⁴⁹ TICE.PT. (n.d.). *Gaia-X Hub Portugal*. <https://tice.pt/gaia-x>

⁵⁰ TICE.PT. (2025). *Gaia-X Hub Portugal 2025 Plan*. https://tice.pt/sites/default/files/2025-04/gaia-x_hub_portugal_2025_plan.pdf

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and transparently governed. These guidelines are the vision that upholds the means for integration, beyond the technical components that enable the Gaia-X Framework, in order to enable a truly federated and interoperable European data ecosystem.

3. Data Security and Privacy

Due to the intrinsic interconnection between Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and smart services within the broader framework of smart cities, a substantial volume of personal data is continuously collected from users, devices, and applications⁵¹.

Cross-sectoral Data Sharing (CDS) is regarded as a critical component for the effective development of smart cities and is essential for enabling the creation of efficient, data-driven urban solutions⁵². The integration of diverse datasets can yield valuable insights that foster collaboration among stakeholders, thereby facilitating more informed and evidence-based decision-making processes⁵³. By promoting data interoperability and reducing information silos, CDS addresses several core challenges associated with smart city implementation, including those related to data integration, governance, privacy, and security⁵⁴.

Moreover, the exchange and dissemination of information among various stakeholders - ranging from individuals to organisations - is facilitated by multiple sharing platforms that play a pivotal role in enabling the operational efficiency of smart cities⁵⁵. Technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, fog computing, and blockchain represent key enablers of these data-sharing processes⁵⁶. Nevertheless, the extensive circulation of personal information within smart city ecosystems poses significant privacy concerns, potentially exposing individuals to severe risks that compromise the confidentiality and security of their data⁵⁷.

⁵¹ Martínez-Ballesté, A., Pérez-Martínez, P. A., & Solanas, A. (2013). The pursuit of citizens' privacy: A privacy-aware smart city is possible. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 51(6), 136–141. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2013.6525606>

⁵² Dessai, A., & Javidroozi, V. (2021). Cross-sectoral process modelling for smart city development. *Business Process Management Journal*, 27(7), 2051–2074. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-05-2021-0333>

⁵³ Tumpa, R. J., & Naeni, L. (2025). Improving decision-making and stakeholder engagement at project governance using digital technology for sustainable infrastructure projects. *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*, 14(4), 1292–1329. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SASBE-10-2024-0451>

⁵⁴ Kusumastuti, R. D., Kurniawan, B., & Suharyono, M. (2022). Analyzing the factors that influence the seeking and sharing of information on the smart city digital platform: Empirical evidence from Indonesia. *Technology in Society*, 68, 101876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.101876>

⁵⁵ Viale Pereira, G., Parycek, P., Falco, E., & Kleinhans, R. (2017). Increasing collaboration and participation in smart city governance: A cross-case analysis of smart city initiatives. *Information Technology for Development*, 23(3), 526–553. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2017.1353946>

⁵⁶ Nair, M. M., & Tyagi, A. K. (2023). AI, IoT, blockchain, and cloud computing: The necessity of the future. *Distributed Computing to Blockchain*, 189–206. Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-96146-2.00001-2>

⁵⁷ Ismagilova, E., Hughes, L., Dwivedi, Y. K., & Raman, R. (2022). Security, privacy and risks within smart cities: Literature review and development of a smart city interaction framework. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 24(2), 393–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-020-10044-1>

Compliance with Data Protection Legislation (DPL) represents one of the most significant challenges to CDS, particularly given the extensive volume of sensitive data generated and processed within smart city environments. DPL frameworks are fundamental to safeguarding individual privacy and ensuring the security of sensitive data within smart city infrastructures⁵⁸. However, while such regulatory measures are designed to protect personal information, they may simultaneously introduce complexities that hinder the efficiency and fluidity of data sharing across sectors.

According to GDPR, sensitive data refers to categories of personal information that require enhanced protection due to their potential to reveal highly sensitive or private attributes. This includes data about racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic information, biometric identifiers used for unique identification, health-related details, or information concerning an individual's sexual orientation or sex life. In contrast, non-sensitive data encompasses personal information that does not fall within these special categories, such as names, contact information, identification numbers, online identifiers, and other general personal data that do not require the heightened safeguards associated with sensitive data⁵⁹.

The key security aspects that must be considered are: i) data confidentiality and secure data storage and transmission, ii) data integrity and availability, iii) privacy protection, iv) access control and authentication, v) data provenance and accountability, vi) interoperability with security and trust management, viii) data governance and policy compliance, and ix) resilience and incident response.

Data confidentiality guarantee prevents unauthorised access to sensitive data. Connected devices play a crucial role across various layers of smart city architectures by facilitating data collection, transmission, temporary storage, and, in some cases, preliminary data analysis⁶⁰. One of the most effective approaches to enhancing the confidentiality of communications within smart cities is the development of lightweight cryptographic techniques for data encryption and decryption, as well as for establishing shared secret keys

⁵⁸ Zaguir, N. A., de Magalhães, G. H., & de Mesquita Spinola, M. (2024). Challenges and enablers for GDPR compliance: Systematic literature review and future research directions. *IEEE Access*, 12, 81608–81630. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3406724>

⁵⁹ Edwards, L. (2016). Privacy, security and data protection in smart cities: A critical EU law perspective. *European Data Protection Law Review*, 2(1), 28–58. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2711290>

⁶⁰ Popescu, D., & Genete, L.-D. (2016). Data security in smart cities: challenges and solutions. *Informatica Economică*, 20(1), 29–36. <https://doi.org/10.12948/issn14531305/20.1.2016.03>

among distributed network nodes. However, implementing such security mechanisms across diverse network components presents a significant challenge due to the heterogeneity of devices connected to smart city infrastructures, which vary widely in computational capacity, communication protocols, and data handling capabilities. Another major challenge in securing smart city communications involves designing an efficient distributed key management system, which is essential given the geographically dispersed nature of smart city networks⁶¹. In such systems, the key management centre is typically responsible for generating primary cryptographic keys—both public and private—with appropriate key lengths and lifetimes. These parameters must be carefully configured to achieve the required security objectives while minimising the risk of depleting the limited computational and energy resources of embedded systems.

Availability refers to the requirement that devices and services should always remain accessible and operational. Within the context of smart systems and applications, this implies the capability to sustain effective functionality even in the presence of security attacks or system disruptions. Given the susceptibility of these systems to various forms of cyber threats, it is imperative that smart infrastructures possess mechanisms for anomaly detection and damage prevention, enabling them to identify abnormal conditions promptly and mitigate potential harm. Resilience is conceptualised as the system's ability to resist, tolerate, and recover from attacks, faults, and large-scale failures⁶¹. To achieve this, protection mechanisms must exhibit strong robustness and an adaptive learning capacity to counter increasingly sophisticated and intelligent cyberattacks.

Furthermore, ensuring the integrity of both IoT devices and data exchanged between devices and cloud infrastructures is of critical importance⁶². As data is transmitted across numerous interconnected devices within a smart ecosystem, they are more vulnerable to tampering during transmission if not sufficiently protected, compared to a laptop or a mobile phone, for example. While security mechanisms such as firewalls and secure communication protocols can regulate data traffic within IoT networks, they often fail to ensure endpoint data integrity due to the limited computational capabilities of IoT devices.

⁶¹ Chakrabarty, S., & Engels, D. W. (2016). A secure IoT architecture for smart cities. *13th IEEE Annual Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC)*, 812–813.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/CCNC.2016.7444889>

⁶² Malik, A., & Om, H. (2017). Cloud computing and Internet of Things integration: Architecture, applications, issues, and challenges. *Sustainable Cloud and Energy Services: Principles and Practice*, 1–24. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-62238-5_1

While privacy is traditionally accepted as an individual's right to be unobserved or undisturbed, this definition becomes increasingly inadequate in the context of emerging and rapidly advancing technologies. Modern technological systems enable observation and monitoring that extend beyond the purely physical realm. For instance, when information about an individual is recorded, stored, and subsequently disclosed, aspects of that person's existence are effectively observed, potentially constituting a violation of their privacy. Given that smart cities are fundamentally information-driven, privacy must be examined from the perspective that the data representing an individual is equivalent to tangible, physical aspects of that individual's identity. The main challenges related to data privacy in the context of smart cities are: i) data collection and surveillance, ii) data ownership and control, iii) cybersecurity threats and iv) informed consent⁶³.

Smart cities use sensors, cameras, and other monitoring technologies to gather real-time data. However, the extensive surveillance of public spaces raises significant concerns regarding the potential intrusion into individual privacy, as continuous monitoring may lead to the unauthorised observation of citizens' behaviours and activities⁶⁴.

The question of data ownership and governance within smart cities is inherently complex⁶⁵. Data generated through urban infrastructure involves multiple stakeholders, including private companies, municipal authorities, and individual citizens, whose interests may conflict. Such dynamics create ambiguities surrounding access rights, control, and permissible usage of collected data.

The highly interconnected nature of smart city systems increases their susceptibility to cybersecurity breaches. Unauthorised access or attacks targeting the network infrastructure can compromise sensitive information, thereby undermining the privacy and security of residents.

Numerous smart city initiatives collect data from residents without obtaining explicit, informed consent. Upholding privacy rights necessitates mechanisms that ensure citizens

⁶³ Elmaghraby, A. S., & Losavio, M. M. (2014). Cyber security challenges in smart cities: Safety, security and privacy. *Journal of Advanced Research*, 5(4), 491–497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2014.02.006>

⁶⁴ Ismagilova, E., Hughes, L., Dwivedi, Y. K., & Raman, R. (2022). Security, privacy and risks within smart cities: Literature review and development of a smart city interaction framework. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 24(2), 393–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-020-10044-1>

⁶⁵ Choenni, S., Bargh, M. S., Busker, T., & Netten, N. (2022). Data governance in smart cities: Challenges and solution directions. *Journal of Smart Cities and Society*, 1(1), 31–51. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SCS-210119>

are fully informed about data collection practices and are provided with clear options to opt in or opt out of participation⁶⁶.

The effectiveness of Internet of Things systems and devices relies on their ability to share data, integrate multiple inputs, and process information to generate added value.

Consequently, it is crucial to establish robust mechanisms for data control and management, ensuring that data generated by IoT devices is not misused or accessed in unauthorised or unintended ways. Authentication within IoT systems, achieved through the establishment of secure communication channels among connected devices, constitutes a critical prerequisite for smart cities⁶⁷. It enables the authorised management of access control for legitimate users while preventing unauthorised entities from accessing system resources. To facilitate secure communications and access management, a variety of authentication and access control protocols have been developed, including Identity-Based Encryption, Attribute-Based Encryption, and Role-Based Access Control. These protocols are particularly essential in cloud-based smart city environments, where citizens' data are often collected and outsourced to distributed storage systems managed by external Cloud Service Providers that may not be fully trusted⁶⁸. Such mechanisms enable smart city applications to securely manage authorised users and revoke access rights when necessary. For instance, attribute-based access control leverages the attributes associated with data owners, users, and IoT devices to enforce fine-grained data access policies, thereby enhancing both the security and privacy of data within smart city ecosystems.

Data provenance refers to metadata structures that document the origin, transformation, access, and ownership of data throughout its lifecycle⁶⁹. In the context of IoT-enabled smart cities, data provenance enhances data quality by enabling traceability, integrity verification, and trustworthiness. It allows systems to identify anomalies, detect errors, validate inputs used for decision-making, and ensure compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks. To address the complexities of data management in such environments, provenance tracking

⁶⁶ Kitchin, R. (2016). The ethics of smart cities and urban science. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 374(2083), 20160115. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2016.0115>

⁶⁷ Al-Turjman, F., Zahmatkesh, H., & Shahroze, R. (2022). An overview of security and privacy in smart cities' IoT communications. *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, 33(3), e367. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.3677>

⁶⁸ Alam, T. (2021). Cloud-based IoT applications and their roles in smart cities. *Smart Cities*, 4(3), 1196–1219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities4030064>

⁶⁹ Hu, R., Yan, Z., & Ding, W. (2020). A survey on data provenance in IoT. *World Wide Web*, 23, 1441–1463. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11280-019-00746-1>

can be employed to maintain a complete history of transformations for all data fragments distributed across multiple nodes. Establishing a comprehensive record of data lifecycle involves capturing detailed information about data generation, transmission, and exchange within the smart city network, as well as documenting subsequent storage, processing, access, and modification activities. Verifying the origin and historical evolution of data is crucial in IoT systems, as it facilitates accuracy assessments, anomaly detection, device auditing, and overall validation of data quality and integrity. Blockchain, as a digital ledger technology, audit trails, and accountability frameworks can be used to ensure data provenance and provide accountability⁷⁰.

Security concerns within smart cities are relevant across all forms of interoperability, as these systems frequently handle sensitive information related to domains such as long-term remote healthcare management, telesurgery, smart grids, and real-time traffic monitoring⁷¹. Consequently, robust access control and vulnerability analysis mechanisms are essential to ensure the protection of such data. Mechanisms that maintain service availability and implement secure user authentication and authorisation protocols must therefore be prioritised. However, the diversity of existing IoT platforms presents a significant challenge, as most are developed according to distinct standards and employ heterogeneous security mechanisms. For instance, token-based authorisation systems used to verify access permissions for different resources and services often rely on platform-specific algorithms and security policies⁷². This lack of uniformity renders cross-platform access control infeasible, thereby introducing additional security limitations. As such, issues related to heterogeneous security architectures and inconsistent policy frameworks must be systematically addressed.

Furthermore, the implementation of an effective identity management mechanism is critical for accurately authenticating end-users of smart city services and securely managing their

⁷⁰ Nair, M. M., & Tyagi, A. K. (2023). AI, IoT, blockchain, and cloud computing: The necessity of the future. *Distributed Computing to Blockchain*, 189–206. Academic Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-96146-2.00001-2>

⁷¹ Biswas, S., Yao, Z., Yan, L., Alqhatani, A., Bairagi, A. K., Asiri, F., & Masud, M. (2023). Interoperability Benefits and Challenges in Smart City Services: Blockchain as a Solution. *Electronics*, 12(4), 1036.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12041036>

⁷² Dammak, M., Boudia, O. R. M., Messous, M. A., Senouci, S. M., & Gransart, C. (2019). Token-based lightweight authentication to secure IoT networks. *16th IEEE Annual Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCNC.2019.8651825>

digital identities⁷³. Network security must also safeguard users' personal information within communication data, ensuring both the reliability and integrity of transmitted information. In addition, security mechanisms should be established to protect data exchanges between various IoT devices and the middleware responsible for data integration.

From a logical perspective, an active and decentralised trust management system should be developed to account for vulnerabilities and emerging threats⁷⁴. Continuous risk assessment processes must support this system to maintain a dynamic and resilient security posture within the smart city ecosystem.

Data governance and policy compliance establish the principles governing how data is shared, used, and protected, primarily relying on governance frameworks that define data-sharing agreements and ensure adherence to legal and ethical standards⁷⁵. Effective data governance models provide structured approaches that facilitate implementation, clarify stakeholder roles and responsibilities, and align data practices with broader public objectives.

However, governance frameworks specific to urban context remain limited. In contrast to relatively stable and centralised structures of corporate environments, cities operate within complex ecosystems marked by overlapping mandates, distributed responsibilities, real-time and unstructured data flows, and open data initiatives, all of which must be managed under conditions of heightened public accountability. Smart cities should establish a comprehensive data governance framework that ensures the integration of appropriate data, algorithms, human expertise, and policy mechanisms to foster trust, transparency, accountability, and responsibility⁷⁶. Such a framework should incorporate: i) high-quality data, free from representational, measurement, evaluation, aggregation, population,

⁷³ Hassan, Y. G., Collins, A., Babatunde, G. O., Abidemi, A., & Mustapha, S. D. (2023). Blockchain and zero-trust identity management system for smart cities and IoT networks. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 4(1), 704–709.

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⁷⁴ Ramachandran, G. S., Radhakrishnan, R., & Krishnamachari, B. (2018). Towards a decentralized data marketplace for smart cities. *2018 IEEE International Smart Cities Conference (ISC2)*, 1–8.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ISC2.2018.8656952>

⁷⁵ Choenni, S., Bargh, M. S., Busker, T., & Netten, N. (2022). Data governance in smart cities: Challenges and solution directions. *Journal of Smart Cities and Society*, 1(1), 31–51.

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⁷⁶ Gharaibeh, A., Salahuddin, M. A., Hussini, S. J., Khreishah, A., Khalil, I., Guizani, M., & Al-Fuqaha, A. (2017). Smart cities: A survey on data management, security, and enabling technologies. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 19(4), 2456–2501.

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sampling, or data-linking biases; ii) responsible algorithms, designed to uphold the principles of accountability, explainability, and fairness, iii) Qualified and diverse human expertise, encompassing a multidisciplinary mix of professionals capable of addressing issues related to inclusion and equity; and iv) robust policies and standards, which provide the institutional and regulatory foundations necessary for ethical data use and sustainable smart city development.

Together, these components form the basis for a governance model that supports ethical decision-making and reinforces public confidence in smart city systems.

Organisations responsible for implementing smart city technologies should develop, evaluate, and maintain comprehensive contingency plans to ensure the manual operation of all critical infrastructure functions, accompanied by appropriate staff training⁷⁷. These contingency measures should include provisions for isolating infrastructure systems, either from one another or from the public internet, to enable autonomous functioning when necessary. In the event of a compromised system, organisations must be equipped to isolate affected components and maintain the operation of the remaining infrastructure with minimal disruption. Furthermore, these organisations should establish, support, and routinely test backup mechanisms for both information technology system records and manual operational capabilities related to the physical systems integrated within the smart city network. Clear identification of how and where data are collected, processed, stored, and transmitted is essential, ensuring that every node within the data lifecycle is adequately protected. System administrators should maintain isolated IT backups, stored separately from primary systems, to prevent the propagation of ransomware attacks, as many ransomware variants are designed to locate, encrypt, or delete accessible backups. Ensuring the physical and logical separation of backup systems enables the restoration of systems and data to their previous operational state in the event of a security breach or ransomware incident.

⁷⁷ Berkeley, Alfred R., Mike Wallace, and Constellation Co. (2010). *A framework for establishing critical infrastructure resilience goals: Final report and recommendations by the council*. National Infrastructure Advisory Council.
<https://www.dhs.gov/xlibrary/assets/niac/niac-a-framework-for-establishing-critical-infrastructure-resilience-goals-2010-10-19.pdf>

4. Data and AI

Data refers to raw values without context; for example, the number 15 alone has no meaning. Information emerges when context is added, such as specifying that 15 represents a person's age. Knowledge is created when information is analysed and connected with experience, for instance, recognising that a 15-year-old is legally considered a minor. Ultimately, wisdom emerges when this knowledge is applied to inform sound judgments, such as developing effective public policies to support youth. Data Science operates across these levels, transforming data into information, information into knowledge, and ultimately supporting wisdom in decision-making following the DIKW hierarchy⁷⁸.

The role of Data Science (DS) in decision-making is increasingly important. As an interdisciplinary field, DS combines computer science, machine learning, mathematics, statistics, domain expertise, software engineering, and traditional research. It uses scientific methods, algorithms, and systems to extract knowledge and insights from both structured and unstructured data⁷⁹.

At its core, Data Science is about discovering knowledge. Knowledge discovery is the process of uncovering patterns and insights from data. This involves working with various types of data, including text, images, numbers, and other formats, usually through data mining techniques. Knowledge discovery and data mining have transformed research practices, especially in the social sciences, by combining domain-specific expertise such as sociology, psychology, economics, and linguistics with technical skills in data processing, database technologies, and computational algorithms. By revealing hidden patterns, these methods promote innovation and support the development of new theories across multiple disciplines.⁸⁰

Building on this foundation, Artificial Intelligence (AI) emerges as a vital enabler for extracting value from Data Spaces and federated data ecosystems. While the development of interoperable and sovereign Data Spaces ensures the availability of reliable and secure

⁷⁸ Rowley, J. (2007). The wisdom hierarchy: representations of the DIKW hierarchy. *Journal of Information Science*, 33(2), 163–180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551506070706>

⁷⁹ Portela, F. (2021). Data Science and Knowledge Discovery. *Future Internet*, 13(7), 178. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi13070178>

⁸⁰ Shu, X., & Ye, Y. (2023). Knowledge Discovery: Methods from data mining and machine learning. *Social Science Research*, 110, 102817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2022.102817>

data, AI offers the means to convert this data into actionable knowledge, thereby supporting innovation, governance, and citizen-centric decision-making. Data validation and sharing are essential to improve the results of DS models and enhance the decision-making process.

4.1 The Decision-Making Process

The decision-making process can be organised into five phases, adapted from Herbert Simon's⁸¹ classical model extended with implementation and monitoring stages:

1. Intelligence – recognising and analysing problems or opportunities through gathering and organising relevant data. AI can assist with anomaly detection, trend recognition, and early warning systems.
2. Design – Development and evaluation of solution alternatives. AI-driven simulations and digital twins allow for the exploration of different scenarios under various constraints.
3. Choice – selection of the most suitable alternative. Predictive models and optimisation algorithms quantify risks and outcomes, supporting evidence-based choices.
4. Implementation – Execution of the selected solution within the organisational context, where AI agents can automate workflows and resource allocation.
5. Optimisation – monitoring results and refining decisions. Generative AI can automatically generate insights and reports, supporting ongoing evaluation and improvement.

Both steps are inherently cyclical, enabling the process to revisit earlier phases whenever refinements are needed to improve outcomes. During the optimisation phase, the results obtained are systematically evaluated and used to refine the implemented solutions, creating a continuous feedback loop.

When applied to Data Spaces, this iterative process establishes the foundation for trustworthy and interoperable data ecosystems. Artificial Intelligence (AI) provides the ability

⁸¹ Campitelli, G., & Gobet, F. (2010). Herbert Simon's Decision-Making Approach: Investigation of Cognitive Processes in Experts. *Review of General Psychology*, 14(4), 354–364. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021256>

to transform data into actionable strategies throughout all stages of the decision cycle, particularly during the implementation and optimisation phases.

4.2 Data Science approaches

In decision-making, data can support three main types of analysis: descriptive analytics, which explain what has happened; predictive analytics, which estimate what is likely to occur; and prescriptive analytics, which recommend the best actions to achieve desired outcomes.

- Descriptive Analytics concentrates on understanding what has occurred by compiling and analysing historical data. Technologies such as Data Warehouses (DW), Online Analytical Processing (OLAP), and dashboarding tools are essential, enabling governments and organisations to monitor key indicators, identify anomalies, and assess past performance.
- Predictive Analytics aims to estimate what is likely to happen using advanced statistical and computational methods. Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques, such as clustering, association, regression, and classification, can be applied to structured and unstructured data, including text, images, and sensor streams. In public administration, predictive models support use cases such as traffic forecasting, fraud detection in social benefits, or energy demand prediction.
- Prescriptive analytics offers recommendations on what actions should be taken by identifying optimal choices within given constraints. This stage combines optimisation models with AI-driven approaches to support resource allocation, policy planning, and service delivery. Generative AI (GAI) increasingly plays a vital role, generating insights and actionable content with fewer technical barriers. GAI can produce natural language summaries for decision-makers, create synthetic datasets for modelling, or power conversational interfaces for citizens. However, it also raises challenges related to bias, transparency, and reliability. Techniques used in predictive analysis can also be applied to enable prescriptive actions.

To ensure a thorough implementation and prevent process errors, a well-established and tested methodology must be followed. Methodologies such as Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD), CRISP-DM (Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining), and SEMMA (Sample, Explore, Modify, Model, Assess) have long provided structured approaches

for guiding data-driven projects, covering stages from data preparation and modelling to evaluation and deployment. Additionally, frameworks from the field of Business Intelligence, such as the Kimball methodology for Data Warehousing, and more recent adaptations for Big Data and AI (e.g., Team Data Science Process (TDSP) and Agile Analytics), extend these principles to contemporary contexts. All of these methodologies are highly relevant to decision-making, as they align with the three main types of analysis: descriptive (understanding past data), predictive (forecasting future outcomes), and prescriptive (optimising and recommending actions).

4.3 Use Cases in Data-Driven

The combination of Data Spaces and AI unlocks multiple opportunities for more innovative and more resilient public services, such as:

- **Urban mobility:** using machine learning models to guess when traffic will get stuck, find open parking spots, or make garbage collection routes better. Federated data can combine several environments to turn the solution global.
- **Reporting on sustainability:** Automating compliance and impact reports using federated environmental data. Employing GenAI methods can assist in creating reports based on reliable data supplied by the federated catalogues. Instead of gathering their own data, it will be possible to utilise global data already collected and validated.
- **Citizen engagement:** Chatbots powered by GAI that help you quickly access public services or assist people in using a service or answering their questions. Federated data can be used as a knowledge base for the chatbot.
- **Energy efficiency:** By using predictive ML to optimise consumption and Data Spaces from different sectors and experiences, it is possible to develop more efficient solutions than by using only one's own data.

4.4 Federated Data Spaces and AI

Federated data spaces are decentralised ecosystems for secure and interoperable data sharing. Catalogues are created by multiple trusted organisations that collaborate under common rules and standards, maintaining complete control over their own datasets. Instead

of centralising data in a single repository, these ecosystems utilise shared infrastructure, governance mechanisms, and service layers to facilitate data exchange across different domains.

A federated network allows data access while maintaining decentralisation and control over ownership. It facilitates discovery, management, and policy enforcement across diverse Data Spaces through shared service layers such as catalogues, trusted data intermediaries, and compliance mechanisms. This method enables federated Data Spaces to promote innovation and collective intelligence, unlocking value that a single organisation alone could not attain.

The use of AI could unlock the hidden knowledge within Data Spaces. AI models trained on high-quality and validated datasets, available through federated catalogues, are more reliable, precise, and context-aware than models trained on isolated or synthetic data. This approach is particularly transformative in research and higher education. Universities and research centres can access a wide range of dependable datasets, supporting interdisciplinary projects, reproducible experiments, and the development of new algorithms with practical applications. At the same time, risks such as the dissemination of fake or altered data must be addressed directly to sustain trust and ensure AI is used ethically and responsibly within these systems.

The European AI Act⁸² classifies some public applications as 'high-risk', requiring them to provide explicit guarantees of fairness, transparency, and traceability. When public data is used, the user must ensure that the sources are reliable and verified. Ethical considerations, including bias, accountability, and inclusiveness, should remain a priority when adopting AI. Gaia-X and federated Data Spaces offer an excellent framework to meet these demands, integrating data sovereignty, auditability, and policy-driven governance seamlessly.

Gaia-X offers a robust framework for addressing the multifaceted challenges of data sharing, privacy, and governance in smart city ecosystems. By promoting a federated and transparent data infrastructure, Gaia-X enables cross-sectoral data sharing (CDS) while ensuring compliance with European data protection legislation such as GDPR. Its architecture supports secure data exchange between diverse stakeholders—citizens,

⁸² EU Artificial Intelligence Act. (n.d.). *Up-to-date developments and analyses of the EU AI Act*. <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

municipalities, and private entities—without compromising confidentiality or control over personal information.

One of Gaia-X’s core strengths lies in its emphasis on data sovereignty and interoperability. Through standardized protocols and trusted identity management, Gaia-X facilitates seamless integration across heterogeneous IoT platforms and cloud environments, mitigating issues related to fragmented security architectures and inconsistent access control mechanisms. This is particularly vital for smart cities, where data flows are real-time, decentralized, and often span multiple domains.

Moreover, Gaia-X’s governance model aligns with the ethical and legal imperatives of smart city development. It provides mechanisms for transparent data provenance, accountability, and policy compliance, ensuring that data lifecycle management—from collection to processing and storage—is traceable and auditable. This supports the creation of resilient infrastructures capable of withstanding cyber threats while maintaining service availability and public trust.

By embedding principles of fairness, explainability, and inclusivity into its data governance framework, Gaia-X empowers cities to build responsible algorithms and leverage multidisciplinary expertise. This fosters ethical decision-making and reinforces citizen confidence in digital urban services. In essence, Gaia-X serves as a foundational pillar for building smart cities that are not only technologically advanced but also secure, equitable, and human-centric.

5. Positioning of the Smart Communities WG of Gaia-X Hub Portugal in the Data-Driven Public Administration Ecosystem

The Smart Communities Working Group (SCWG) of Gaia-X Hub Portugal is positioned to act as an enabling instrument of the transition from data-centred to data-driven public administration. As a national contact node within Gaia-X, the mission of this WG is to promote the use of federated, trustworthy, and sovereign data infrastructures that will enable interoperability, transparency, and innovation in Portuguese Smart Cities.

This positioning is in tune with the shared European vision whereby data is a key public asset and an enabler of evidence-based decision-making, digital sovereignty, and citizen-centric governance. The SCWG will bridge technological, regulatory, and organisational domains to operationalise the principles of data federation, trust, and interoperability in the particular administrative and territorial context of Portugal.

5.1 Strategic Vision

The strategic vision of the Gaia-X Hub Portugal is built upon three interconnected pillars:

- **Digital Sovereignty and European Interoperability:** Trying to ensure that Portuguese Public Administrations are able to contribute to European data federations while maintaining full control of their data. It means conformity to the Data Governance Act, Data Act, and European Interoperability Framework, which guarantees data sharing for both the national and cross-border sphere in light of privacy and security concerns, alongside compliance with EU and national laws. The interoperability between Portuguese Data Spaces and the European ones will be ensured by implementing GXFS and the Trust Framework of Gaia-X, through a common governance model and, in particular, through transparent certification and verifiable interoperability.
- **Public Value Creation through Data Spaces:** Public administrations should not just be data collectors; they should be active players contributing to the creation of

economic, social, and environmental value within Common European Data Spaces. Gaia-X enables municipalities, inter-municipal communities, regional authorities, and national agencies to act simultaneously as data providers, consumers, and federators in the collaborative ecosystem that it empowers. It will lay the foundation for enhanced efficiency, resilience, and innovation of public services. It promotes data-driven governance as an enabler of digital transformation for smart, responsive, and evidence-based development of public policies.

- **Capacity Building and Governance Innovation:** Gaia-X Hub Portugal mentions that technological innovation must be combined with institutional and human capacity building. Therefore, the Hub promotes dissemination, and technical assistance actions to adopt Gaia-X principles, open standards such as DCAT-AP, NGS-LD, ISO 37120, and ethics frameworks related to data and Artificial Intelligence. It also underpins experimentation and testing via pilot projects, creating living labs in which the public entities can test new models of data governance under real operational conditions.

5.2 National Positioning and Stakeholder Ecosystem

Through the Working Group, the Hub provides a neutral multi-stakeholder platform for defining the reference architecture, interoperability standards, and certification mechanisms for national data spaces.

The Hub works in close coordination with current national strategies for digital transformation, such as the Action Plan for Digital Transition, the Cloud Strategy for Public Administration in Portugal, and the Portugal Digital Agenda, trying to ensure that national initiatives related to open data, AI governance, and digital infrastructure merge with European Gaia-X initiatives.

At the same time, it establishes links with the Gaia-X European Association and other national hubs so that the Portuguese use cases will contribute to the European catalogue of federated data spaces in key domains like mobility, energy, public sector innovation, while also creating opportunities for Portugal to actively benefit from international data spaces.

This positioning further asserts the role of Portugal as an active contributor to the European data economy and as a testbed for trusted and sovereign digital ecosystems.

5.3 Guiding Principles

The operational positioning of Gaia-X Hub Portugal is based on guiding principles that ensure coherence among technical implementation, governance, and societal impact:

- **Openness and Interoperability:** the new developments enabled by the Hub are based on open standards and interfaces, so as to enable long-term interoperability and to avoid technological lock-in.
- **Trust and Transparency:** each actor in the ecosystem acts in verifiable compliance and transparent usage control, enabling accountable and ethical data exchange. The principle of subsidiarity and territorial coherence means that data governance should be in full accordance with the territorial structure of Portugal, from municipal, intermunicipal, and regional to national levels, by ensuring multi-level coordination while taking care of the autonomy of each tier.
- **Citizen-centric design:** public value and citizen trust are at the core of all data-driven projects. Gaia-X Hub Portugal advocates for the use of data governance models that make sure of the following: privacy, inclusion, and accessibility.
- **Sustainability and Resilience:** designing data infrastructures and services taking into account criteria of environmental and social sustainability as stated by the United Nations SDGs.

The vision of the SCWG is a near future where data spaces for public administration, mobility, energy, and smart territories are operating in full federation to allow real-time collaboration between local authorities, citizens, and private partners. It calls for continued investment in semantic interoperability, assurance of data quality, and secure, federated infrastructures, anchored in trust and transparency. With its positioning, the WG commits to acting as a national competence centre for federated data governance, enabling the development of a resilient, interoperable, and data-driven public sector that fully respects European principles of digital sovereignty and societal trust.

6. Use Cases

TEADAL

Website: <https://teadal.eu/>

Responsible Entity: Ubiwhere

Involved Partners: Ubiwhere

Participating Cities: São João da Madeira

Funding Programme: Horizon Europe

Thematic Areas: Federated and sovereign data infrastructure

Description:

TEADAL aims to develop foundational technologies that enable trustworthy, mediatorless federations of data lakes spanning the cloud-edge continuum. By supporting dynamic, cross-organisational data sharing with strong guarantees of privacy, confidentiality, and energy efficiency, TEADAL contributes to a sustainable and sovereign European Digital Single Market.

A central foundation for TEADAL's architecture is the Gaia-X federated and secure data infrastructure. Gaia-X provides critical building blocks such as data sovereignty, service federation, and compliance with the IDS reference architecture model. These principles guide the design of TEADAL's federation mechanisms, ensuring that data sharing remains aligned with European values and legal frameworks.

TEADAL's federated data lake approach enables verifiable and policy-compliant data flows across heterogeneous systems, without relying on central mediators. This is especially relevant in public sector contexts where sensitive data must be shared responsibly and sustainably across institutions and jurisdictions.

Start and End date: 1/09/2022 - 31/10/2025

BeOpen

Website: <https://beopen-dep.eu/>

Responsible Entity: Engineering Group

Involved Partners: Ubiwhere

Participating Cities: Porto

Funding Programme: The Digital Europe Programme

Thematic Areas: Open data interoperability, High Value Datasets (HVDs), AI-enhanced services

Description:

BeOpen aims to enable the development of new digital and AI services by facilitating access to and use of European Union (EU) Public Sector High Value Datasets (HVDs) through a comprehensive framework that improves interoperability, semantics, and quality of public sector data. The project addresses a critical challenge: despite the increased open data production from public authorities, data utilisation by third-party services remains limited.

BeOpen establishes a comprehensive framework for managing open data and metadata throughout their entire lifecycle, following FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This approach supports the creation of future Data Spaces on the sustainable city domain. The solution encompasses open source tools, replicable pipeline and ontologies, and best practices to perform data collection, curation, semantic annotation, data and metadata harmonisation, improve quality and publish in machine-readable format (in bulk or via APIs). The framework addresses multiple data domains including statistics, mobility, environmental monitoring, earth observation, and geo-spatial information, while ensuring compliance with legal interoperability requirements.

The framework is deployed and evaluated through pilot implementations across six European countries (Germany, Greece, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, and Spain), demonstrating its practical applicability in diverse public sector contexts.

Start and End date: 1/01/2023 - 30/06/2025

ioCity

Website: <https://iocity.research.iotech.pt/>

Responsible Entity: IOTECH

Involved Partners: IOTECH

Participating Cities: Vila Nova de Famalicão

Funding Programme: Portugal2020

Thematic Areas: Smart mobility, Mobility prediction, Urban transportation, Real-time monitoring

Description:

The ioCity project developed an intelligent web/mobile application aimed at improving urban mobility through real-time data, prediction, and integration across urban systems. The project addresses challenges common to many European cities: congestion, under-utilisation or unpredictability of public transport, insufficient information for parking availability, and lack of integrated, real-time mobility services.

ioCity provides users with up-to-date information on public transport status (including occupancy), parking availability, and route suggestions across different transport modes. It employs advanced mathematical models and Artificial Intelligence to forecast occupancy levels (for both public transport and parking), enabling better planning and more informed decisions by citizens and city authorities. To achieve better results, the system is ready to interoperate with real-time city data.

ioCity has been developed and tested in Vila Nova de Famalicão City through a Portugal 2020 project. The solution can monitor parked vehicles and interoperate with existing monitoring systems.

Start and End date: 1/10/2021 - 30/06/2023

ioCity - Test Bed

Responsible Entity: IOTECH

Involved Partners: IT - Instituto de Telecomunicações

Participating Cities: Aveiro

Funding Programme: PRR

Thematic Areas: Artificial Intelligence, Smart Mobility, Internet of Things, High-Performance Computing

Description:

This pilot project aimed to test and refine a set of analytical and intelligent algorithms for the monitoring and prediction of parking occupancy in real and diverse contexts. Building upon the previous developments from the ioCity project, this new phase leveraged real data from car parks in the city of Aveiro to evaluate the algorithms' performance and adaptability to new environments.

Access to real-world datasets was essential to validate and enhance the analytical and intelligent models, ensuring their applicability in operational contexts. The project specifically focused on testing two complementary approaches:

- Analytical, through Online Analytical Processing (OLAP) to study parking flow and occupancy trends across multiple dimensions (e.g., weather conditions, location, date, and time);
- Predictive, using classification and regression algorithms to estimate, in real time, the probability and number of available parking spaces in selected areas of Aveiro.

Originally developed within ioCity research project and validated in laboratory environments (TRL4) with data from Vila Nova de Famalicão and Lisbon, the Next Gen Mobility Testbed enabled the transition toward more mature validation (TRL7) by offering real, varied, and dynamic data sources at a new city: Aveiro

Start and End date: 10/11/2024 - 31/07/2025

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